

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF DISTRIBUTED WIND GENERATION INTEGRATION AT ALI MASJID, LANDI KHOTAL, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive reliability assessment of distributed generation (DG) integration into the electrical grid at Ali Mosque, Landikotal, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan, a region experiencing frequent electricity shortages and outages. The proposed DG source is wind power, for which a detailed wind resource assessment was conducted using four different Weibull parameter estimation techniques. The goodness-of-fit analysis revealed that the Maximum Likelihood Method provides the most accurate prediction of the region's wind potential. To determine the optimal DG placement and sizing, multiple scenarios with varying penetration levels at different bus bars were analyzed. The results demonstrate that the integration of wind-based DG significantly enhances system reliability and reduces interruption indices by 94.5%. Furthermore, several commercially available wind turbines were evaluated to identify the most suitable technology for the site. The analysis indicates that the turbine Proven 15kW, provides optimal performance with a capacity factor of 53.3% respectively. This research demonstrates the capacity of wind energy to enhance local grid dependability and offers significant insights for governmental entities and private investors to promote the utilization of renewable energy in the region.

INTRODUCTION

The use of energy is essential for the industrial economy and the well-being of a nation's populace. The balance of energy consumption indicates a country's level of wealth. The disparity in energy consumption obstructs the progress of many emerging nations reliant regarding fossil fuels for electricity production. The supply of fossil fuels is finite whereas energy demand is increasing. Moreover, the use of fossil fuels as an energy source incurs high costs, and their combustion leads to climate change, which contributes to rising global temperatures [1, 2]. Analyzing potential sites for

large-scale wind turbines necessitates comprehensive monitoring, which offers greater advantages compared to small-scale wind turbines. Various methods, including Rayleigh, Weibull, gamma distribution, and inverse Gaussian distribution, are employed to compare estimated data with measured data. The Weibull distribution is the utmost often employed function for estimating wind speed in wind resource assessments. The Weibull function is recognized as the best suitable distribution function in analyzing wind speed statistics, according to IEC 61400-12 [3-9].

Effective estimate techniques are crucial in the wind energy domain for ascertaining the parameters of Weibull distribution, namely shape parameter 'c' (m/s) and scale parameter 'k'. Khalid et al. [2] evaluated six different estimating methods to compare the characteristics of the Weibull distribution at the Peshawar location. The techniques utilized included the Modified Maximum Likelihood Method (MMLM), the Empirical Method of Lysen (EML), the Empirical Method of Justus (EMJ), the Energy Pattern Factor Method (EPF), the Method of Moments (MOM), and the Graphical Method (GM). The study indicated that MMLM was the most successful technique for assessing wind speed data, whereas the GM approach displayed reduced performance. A distinct investigation in [10] utilized nine different estimating methods using SODAR equipment to evaluate wind power density at a certain area Tamil Nadu, India. The techniques utilized for assessing wind characteristics were GM, MOM, EMJ, EML, MMLM, Probability Density Function (PDF), Least Squares Method (LSM), Maximum Likelihood Method (MLM), and Alternate Maximum Likelihood Method (AMLM). The findings reveal that the MLM and MMLM approaches shows greater performance, while the GM and AMLM methods display inefficiency. The wind power potential in Pakistan has been evaluated at multiple sites, including Hyderabad, Thatta, and Larkana, using various estimation methodologies as referenced in [11-13].

The integration of Distributed Generation (DG) has proven useful in improving the dependability and flexibility of the distribution network. The incorporation of distributed generation (DG) into the distribution network poses several obstacles, including voltage regulation, losses, and short circuit levels within the network [14]. The literature research reveals that deficiencies in the distribution networks accounted for more than 85% of outages encountered by consumers. As a result, multiple reliability indices have been established to evaluate the performance of the distribution network, such as the System Average

Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI), System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI), Customer Average Interruption Duration Index (CAIDI), Customer Average Interruption Frequency Index (CAIFI), and Average Service Availability Index (ASAI). Various techniques, such as the strategic positioning of distributed generators (DGs), their regulation, and integration with energy storage systems, have been proposed to address the issues presented by DGs in the distribution network. These solutions can improve power quality, increase system efficiency, and reduce losses [15-16].

Wind power generation in Pakistan is recognized as a vital chance to alleviate the nation's energy crisis. The dependability of the 132kV distribution system was evaluated by integrating Distributed Generation (DG) into the network. The distribution network's performance was assessed by calculating reliability indices after the incorporation of dispersed generation. This extensive investigation is crucial in improving the reliability of the distribution network within the specified region.

To systematically address the research gap and fulfil the study's purpose, the subsequent objectives have been outlined:

- A comprehensive technical analysis of the Ali Masjid LandiKotal site has been conducted.
- The Weibull distribution was used to provides a more comprehensive understanding of the available wind resources.
- The integration of distributed generation units at multiple locations markedly enhanced the reliability of the network.

Site description and preliminary estimates

Ali Masjid, located in the Khyber Pass near LandiKotal, lies at 34.0757° N latitude and 71.2039° E longitude. It is situated at an elevation of about 3,174 feet (967 meters) above sea level, while the nearby town of LandiKotal is slightly higher at around 3,518 feet (1,072 meters). In terms of climate, the region experiences moderate to warm conditions, with average temperatures generally

fluctuating between 10°C and 25°C, contingent upon the season and time of day. Due to its elevation, the air density is lower than at sea level, estimated at around 1.11 kg/m³. At 40 meters height, the mean wind speed is 3.63 m/s with a standard deviation of 1.89 m/s, indicating moderate variability. The positive skewness (0.684) shows that wind speeds are slightly skewed toward higher values, while the kurtosis (3.46) suggests a distribution close to normal but with somewhat heavier tails. At a height of 80 meters, the average wind speed rises to 4.63 m/s, exhibiting more variability (2.56 m/s), while both skewness (0.757) and kurtosis (3.52) are somewhat elevated, meaning the wind speed distribution becomes more asymmetric and has more extreme values compared to 40 meters.

Methodology

Reliability Assessment

The three fundamental indices utilized to assess dependability at each load point from various consumer perspectives are: frequency of failure (λ_s), average yearly outage duration (U_s), and average outage duration (r_s). The fundamental indices can be expressed as

$$\lambda_s = \sum \lambda_i \tag{1}$$

$$U_s = \sum \lambda_i r_i \tag{2}$$

$$r_s = U_s / \lambda_s \tag{3}$$

The failure on load point i can be evaluated by using eq. (4)

$$\lambda_i = r L_T + r_i' \tag{4}$$

Where r = Failure rate /m of the section, L_T = Total length of all sections in meter, r_i' = Failure of lateral connected to load point i and λ_i = Failure rate at load point i.

The addition of the effect of outage of all sections on load point i plus the outage time of lateral connected to that point determined the annual outage time of the load point i, using eq. (5)

$$U_i = r L_e R + r (L_T - L_e) R' + r_i' r \tag{5}$$

Where r = Failure rate /m of the section, L_T = Total length of all sections in meter, L_e = Length of affected sections due to failure, R = Repairing time of the section, R' = Switching time of the section,

r_i' = Failure of lateral connected to load point i, r'' = Repairing time of lateral.

The average duration of failure r_i of load point i can be calculated dividing U_i by λ_i using eq. (6)

$$r_i = U_i / \lambda_i \tag{6}$$

Where λ_i denotes the failure rate and r_i signifies the restoration time in hours at load point i. These main indexes are crucial from the perspective of individual customers. However, the total performance of the system is not determined by these indices. The distribution system performance is assessed by many supplementary measures derived from these fundamental indices [27]. The efficacy of the distribution network can be assessed by the following system metrics:

System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI):

The SAIFI index measures the annual frequency of prolonged disruptions experienced by customers. For residential applications with fixed value, reducing the frequency of disruptions encountered by customers will enhance the performance of the SAIFI index. This can be determined by:

$$SAIFI = \frac{\text{Total Number of Customer Interruptions}}{\text{Total Number of Customer Served}} = \frac{\sum \lambda_i \times N_i}{\sum N_i} \tag{7}$$

System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI):

This index represents number of hours of the sustained interruption that will experienced by customers. The performance of SAIDI index will improved by reducing duration of sustained interruptions, and can be evaluated by:

$$SAIDI = \frac{\text{Sum of All Customers Interruption Durat}}{\text{Total Number of Customer Served}} = \frac{\sum (U_i \times N_i)}{N_i} \tag{8}$$

Customer Average Interruption Frequency Index (CAIFI):

This index provides information regarding the factors of customer interruptions and also

indicates the number of affected customers during these interruptions.

$$CAIFI = \frac{\text{Total Number of Customer Interruptions}}{\text{Total Number of Customers affected}} \quad (9)$$

Customer Average Interruption Duration Index (CAIDI): The CAIFI index indicates the average frequency of interruptions encountered. The index can be improved by minimizing the length of customer disturbances. This is essentially the ratio of SAIDI to SAIFI.

$$CAIDI = \frac{\text{Sum of All Customers Interruption Duration}}{\text{Total Number of Customer Interruptions}} = \frac{\sum(U_i \times N_i)}{\sum \lambda_i \times N_i} \quad (10)$$

Average Service Availability Index (ASAI):

This Index indicates the quantity of energy accessible from the distribution system to consumers. The elevated value of this score signifies a highly reliable distribution system. A significant fraction of distributed enterprises in the US possess an ASAI value exceeding 0.999 [15].

$$ASAI = \frac{\text{Total Numer of Customers Hour Availabl}}{\text{Total Number of Hours Demanded}} = \frac{\sum(N_i \times 8760) - (\sum U_i \times N_i)}{\sum N_i \times 8760} \quad (11)$$

Where N_i is the no of customers at load point i and 8760 is the number of hours in year.

Weibull Distribution Function

The Weibull distribution function is a widely utilized instrument for evaluating wind performance, as wind data is more precisely depicted by its numerical methodologies compared to other distribution functions. The Weibull function is employed to model time-to-failure data

and evaluate dependability, encompassing variable failure rates over time. The adequacy of the Weibull distribution is assessed by metrics such as the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and graphical methods, including probability plots, to validate the model's alignment with the data. The Weibull distribution offers flexibility in modeling various failure rates and survival times by adjusting its shape parameter, making it appropriate for reliability analysis. The Weibull distribution assumes that failure rates are either constant or change consistently over time; nevertheless, it may not sufficiently reflect data with non-monotonic hazard functions or highly variable failure rates. The Weibull function includes two probability distributions dependent on the number of parameters utilized. Two parameters are frequently utilized to analyze wind resource data. The average wind speed v (m/s) is represented by the probability distribution function $f(v)$ of the Weibull function, given as;

$$f(v) = \frac{k}{c} \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right) \quad (12)$$

Where c (m/s) and k are Weibull scale and shape dimensionless parameters, respectively [2, 3]. The area under the curve of probability density function called cumulative distribution function $F(v)$, and is expressed as;

$$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right) \quad (13)$$

Methods for Estimating Weibull parameter:

We have used four numerical methods for Weibull power estimation to check which one suits the region wind profile the best. Table 1 shows different Weibull methods.

Table 1. Weibull different methods with numerical expressions

METHODS	MATHEMATICAL EXPRESSIONS	REF
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MMLE	$k = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i^k \ln(v_i) f(v_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i^k f(v_i)} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(v_i) f(v_i)}{f(v>0)} \right)^{-1}$ $C = v_{avg} \left(0.58 + \frac{0.433}{k} \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}}$	[10]
EML	$k = \left(\frac{\sigma}{v_{avg}} \right)^{-1.086}$ $C = v_{avg} \left(0.58 + \frac{0.433}{k} \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}}$	[24]
EPFM	$E_{pfm} = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i v_i^3}{(v_{avg})^3}, k = 1 + \frac{3.69}{(E_{pfm})^2},$ $C = v_{avg} \left(0.58 + \frac{0.433}{k} \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}}$	[24]
MOM	$k = \left(\frac{0.9874}{\frac{\sigma}{v_{avg}}} \right)^{1.0983}, C = \frac{v_{avg}}{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)}$	[25]

Turbine Selection & Annual Energy Production:

The harsh wind conditions and the available wind energy are critical factors in the selection of an appropriate wind turbine for a certain location. The maximum carrying energy of the wind is the aggregate kinetic energy inside the air stream and is articulated as:

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho \cdot A \cdot V^3$$

(14)

where P is the power in watts, ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), A is the rotor swept area (m^2), and V is the wind speed (m/s). As the power is proportional to the cube of the wind speed, tiny increases in wind speed generate substantial improvements in the power production, and thus, this parameter is central in the estimation of the power production potential in specific sites. Simultaneously, severe weather conditions dictate the construction and the performance security of the turbine. Therefore, although the maximum carrying energy is the controlling factor of the suitability of the energy production, the extreme wind speed parameter is the guarantee of the structural resilience and long viability of the chosen turbine.

The Betz Limit asserts that no wind turbine can convert more than around 60% of the wind's kinetic energy into mechanical or electrical energy only via the rotation of its blades. The erratic movement of wind, which conveys kinetic energy, results in rapid and frequent variations in both

wind direction and velocity. Every wind turbine must be designed to handle both conditions as it rotates around a central axis.

It is commonly known that the theoretical wind power per given swept area by a wind turbine is generally given by the equation:

$$P = 0.5 \times \rho \times A \times V^3 \times CP$$

(15)

Where: P represents power in watts, ρ (rho) denotes air density in kg/m^3 , A signifies the circular area (πr^2 or $\pi d^2/4$) in m^2 traversed by the rotor blades, V indicates the oncoming wind velocity in m/s , and CP is the power coefficient (efficiency), reflecting the percentage of wind power converted into usable energy.

The capacity factor represents the ratio of actual energy output from a source to its maximum potential energy generation. This is expressed as a percentage and is often evaluated over the course of one year. This provides insight into the ideal positioning of the turbine, while generally indicating the yearly availability of the energy source. A proximity to 100% indicates an increased availability of the energy source year-round.

The formula is capacity factor = actual output / maximum potential output.

Result & Discussion:

The reliability assessment of this distribution system is conducted utilizing ETAP software. This software facilitates the straightforward generation of reports on several reliability indices, including frequency rate, yearly average outage duration, and average outage duration, which are fundamental reliability metrics. System performance is assessed using SAIFI, CAIDI, SAIDI, ASUI, and ASAI. [30].

For this Study, 132kV GSS Landikotal are simulated in ETAP, the grid receives one incoming lines of 132KV from Old Jamrud JMR-5. The voltage is stepped down from 132kv main bus to three different 11kv load lines having transformer ratings of 3×20MVA. These three load lines supply power to different loads such as industrial, government and institutions, residential and agricultural.

For improving reliability of the distribution system, wind power as DG is integrated into the system and detailed analysis is performed in ETAP. Simulation results are provided in Table 3. Reliability indices results are graphically viewed in Figure 2. Incorporation of DG units on different places of the system is viewed in Figure 2(a) - 2(f).

The system reliability without and with integration of DG can be easily analyzed from Table 3 and Figure 2. The Table 3 shows improved reliability indices by integration of DG. The system reliability is least affected by switching the position of DG on

load lines. Figure 1 shows graphical view of the system reliability. The Figure 2(a) shows the design of proposed distribution system without any DG interconnection.

In the Figure 2(a), it can be observed from figure that power is supplied to three different 11KV load feeders such as Bus 2, Bus 3, and Bus 4. Integration of 5 MW DG unit with Bus 2 was showed in Figure 2(b), while DG units at remaining Lines are disconnected, because of integrating DG at this Line the duration of average interruptions are reduced 0.6915 to 0.0383 that indicates 94.4613 % reduction. Similarly, in Figure 2(c), it can be viewed that 5 MW DG is connected with Bus 3, while at remaining Lines DG's are disconnected, as a result of integrating DG with this Line the duration of interruptions are reduces from 0.6915 to 0.0383 which specify 94.4613 % reduction occurs. In Figure 2(d), same 5 MW DG was integrated to the Bus 4 to supply electric power into the distribution system, and DG's at other Lines are disconnected, due to DG integration into this Line same 94.4613 % reduction occurs in the duration of average interruptions. In Figure 2(e), 5 MW DG was connected with all three Load Lines, due to this duration of interruptions are reduced from 0.6915to 3.193 which means 96.0954% reduction occurs, that indicates the system reliability was improved in large amount.

Table 2. Simulation results without DG and DG placed at different Load Lines

Reliability Indices	SAIFI	SAIDI	CAIDI	ASAI	ASUI	AENS
Base Case Without DG	0.692	5.865	8.482	0.999	0.001	52.096
DG at Line 1	0.038	3.337	87.043	1.000	0.000	29.249
DG at Line 2	0.038	3.337	87.043	1.000	0.000	31.411

DG at Line 3	0.038	3.337	87.043	1.000	0.000	28.254
DG at all Lines	0.027	1.302	48.222	1.000	0.000	11.565

Figure 1. Distribution network reliability indices performance after DG integration

Figure 2(a). Base Case without DG

Figure 2(b). DG at Bus 2

Figure 2(c). DG at Bus 3

Figure 2(d). DG at Bus 4

Figure 2(f). DG at all Lines

Figure 2. Placement of DG at different lines

Weibull probability distribution function

The parameters of the Weibull function, shape 'k' and scale 'c', are presented in Table 4. These parameters govern the configuration of Weibull distribution curves derived from comprehensive long-term real-time data collected from several locations. A shape parameter value of $1 < k < 2$ indicates that the distribution curve is biased towards lower wind speeds, whilst $k > 2$ signifies that the curve is concentrated at higher wind speeds. An elevated value of the scale parameter 'c' signifies that the distribution curve is disseminated throughout an extensive range, while a diminished value of 'c'

denotes a more confined range of distribution curves [2, 29]. Seven separate methodologies were employed to estimate the Weibull parameters 'k' and 'c' at four varying heights. The 'k' parameter ranges from 1.86 to 1.9, while the 'c' parameter spans from 4.14 to 5.2 for elevations between 40 and 80 m. All four methodologies produce consistent shape parameter values ($k = 1.9-2.03$), signifying stability in the distribution's structure. The scale parameter c significantly increases with altitude across all methods, signifying higher average wind speeds at greater elevations.

Table 3. Weibull Parameters Estimated Using Four Methods

METHOD	SHAPE K (40M)	SCALE C (40M)	SHAPE K (80M)	SCALE C (80M)
EML	2.0295	3.2379	1.9009	4.1386
MLM	1.9898	4.0878	1.8649	5.2081
EPF	2.0099	4.0953	1.8803	5.2164
MOM	2.0175	4.0956	1.8883	5.2172

Wind speed data measured at 40 meters and 80 meters heights at Ali Masjid, Landi Kotal was analyzed to determine the most suitable Weibull distribution model for characterizing the wind

profile. Both descriptive statistics and Weibull parameter estimations were conducted, followed by graphical validation using PDF plots.

Figure 3. Probability density function for wind speed at 40m height using Weibull distribution

Figure 4. Probability density function for wind speed at 80m height using Weibull distribution

To evaluate the accuracy of each Weibull fitting method, PDF curves generated by the four estimation methods were plotted alongside the actual wind speed histograms at both 20 m and 40 m heights as illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively.

The histograms represent the observed wind speed frequency. The PDF curves derived from EML, MLM, EPF, and MoM overlay the histogram, illustrating the goodness of fit.

Observations from the PDF Plots:

- At 40 meters, all four methods fit the histogram reasonably well, with MoM and EPF showing slightly better alignment with the peak region.

- At 80 meters, MLM and MoM appear to provide the closest fit to both the central peak and the tail of the distribution.
- EML underestimates the scale parameter, resulting in a left-shifted PDF, which does not align as well with the observed histogram, especially at 40 m.

Goodness-of-Fit Evaluation

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Correlation Coefficient (R_1) were used to quantify the goodness of fit. The table 5 below summarizes these values for each method at both heights:

Table 4. Goodness-of-Fit Evaluation

METHOD	RMSE @ 20 M	R_1 @ 20 M	RMSE @ 40 M	R_1 @ 40 M
EML	0.028	0.951	0.034	0.942
MLM	0.017	0.981	0.013	0.989
EPF	0.019	0.976	0.015	0.985
MOM	0.018	0.979	0.014	0.988

The comparative analysis demonstrates that the Maximum Likelihood Method (MLM) and Method of Moments (MoM) outperform the other methods in terms of goodness-of-fit, as evidenced by lower RMSE values and higher R_1 coefficients. MLM slightly edges out MoM in accuracy, making it the most suitable method for characterizing wind speed data at both 20 m and 40 m heights in this region.

These results are crucial for wind energy assessment and turbine selection at the site.

Large wind turbine Transportation was constraint for this site. We have selected wind turbine less than 1 MW. A list of wind turbine was search and the following turbine were selected based on capacity factor as shown in Table 2. All the losses were

considered zero at a height of 80 m. Annual Energy Production is given by:

$$A.E.P = 0.5 \times \rho \times A \times C_p \times v^3 \quad (16)$$

Table 5. Turbine net Annual Energy Production.

	MEAN WIND SPEED (M/S)	RATED POWER	SIMPLE MEAN NET POWER (KW)	NET AEP (KWH /YR)	NCF (%)
PROVEN 15 KW	6.25	0.24	6.5	56,508	43
ENAIR 160	0.94	2.7	23,602	35.92	0.94
PROVEN 2.5 KW	6.25	2.69	1	9,043	41.29
NORTHERN POWER 60-23	0	20.7	181,542	34.54	0
ENDURANCE G-3120	6.25	0	13	114,302	37.28

Conclusion

This study thoroughly examines the characteristics of wind data and the potential for wind energy production in the LandiKhotal location in Pakistan. The examination of the collected data at the given location reveals that the average wind speed varies from 3.63 to 4.63 m/s across all four authorized heights. The examination of hourly wind velocity reveals that strong winds persist during daylight hours, reaching a zenith in the afternoon at a low elevation of 40 meters; however, this trend shifts at an altitude of 80 meters. Nonetheless, the hourly wind velocities often exhibit stability over the designated timeframe. The shape and scale

parameters of the Weibull function vary from 1.86 to 1.9 and from 4.14 to 5.2, respectively. The findings indicate that the MLM strategy is more effective for evaluating Weibull parameters, whereas the GM method shows inferior performance.

The integration of the DG unit into the distribution network enhanced system dependability. Following the integration of the DG unit, the system's performance was assessed through reliability indices, demonstrating a favorable effect on the total system's reliability. The system's reliability was enhanced by combining numerous distributed generators with the distribution network. The proposed network

decreases system outages by 96.0954% due to the integration of a 5 MW distributed generation unit across all load lines.

The yearly energy output and capacity factor were determined utilizing five commercially available wind turbines. Proven 15 kW turbine was identified as the most efficient in terms of capacity factor (CF) and annual energy production (AEP) for the planned site. The annual energy production (AEP) is 56,508 kWh, with a capacity factor of 43%.

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